

Woven Heritage: A Comparative Study of Design, Aesthetic, and Symbolism in Mughal and Persian Carpets

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Abstract:

Carpet weaving, an intricate and exquisite art form, has flourished over centuries, functioning as both a practical craft and a significant medium of cultural expression. The Persian and Mughal carpet-making traditions are among the most influential in textile design, each distinguished by artistic depth, technical mastery, and symbolic richness. This study examines how the Mughal Empire reinterpreted Persian carpet aesthetics, blending geometric precision with botanical realism to establish a distinct visual identity. The research explores motifs, color palettes, weaving techniques, and compositions through an analytical comparison of Persian and Mughal carpet designs. The research utilizes historical texts, archival records, and visual analysis. A comparative qualitative methodology is employed to assess design adaptations. Mughal carpets retained Persian symmetry while incorporating local elements, vibrant hues, and realism. Trade and diplomacy fostered cross-cultural exchanges, shaping their evolution and reinforcing both traditions' lasting impact on global textile heritage through adaptation and innovation

Keywords: Carpets, Design, Heritage, Motifs, Mughal, Persia

Citation: Nidhi Yadav, Neha Singh - "Woven Heritage: A Comparative Study of Design, Aesthetic, and Symbolism in Mughal and Persian Carpets", *Journal of the Textile Association*, **86/3** (Sept-Oct'25), 292-300,, <https://www.doi.org/10.63665/>

Article History : Article Received :15-07-2025, Revised: 23-08-2025, Accepted: 27-08-2025

1. Introduction

Carpet weaving, an intricate and sophisticated art form, has a rich and complex history that spans centuries and regions. It serves not only as a functional commodity but also as a fundamental medium of cultural expression. Two of the most esteemed carpet-making traditions that have significantly influenced this field of textile design originated from Persia and the Mughal Empire. Due to their distinct cultural and creative backgrounds, both civilizations are renowned for their mastery of design, techniques, and symbolism [1].

The roots of Persian carpets may be traced back to ancient civilizations. These carpets are known for their intricate geometric patterns, symmetrical designs, and brilliant color schemes, all containing profound symbolic meanings. It was during the Safavid era that the art of carpet weaving developed, and it was at this time, these carpets reached their maximum artistic potential [2]. Arabesques, floral medallions, and garden-inspired themes were some of the most common designs found on Persian carpets.

The Mughal Empire, on the other hand, which rose to prominence in India in the 16th century, was highly affected by Persian artistry, notably in the early phases of carpet manufacture. This was especially true in the early stages of carpet production. However, Mughal artists quickly established their distinctive style by combining Persian methods with local Indian aesthetics. This allowed them to create unique works of art. These carpets have intricate depictions of local flora and wildlife, such as blossoming plants, birds, animals, and geometric patterns inspired by Persian art [3].

These rulers deeply appreciated the arts and encouraged a vibrant cultural interchange between India and Persia. While scholars have extensively studied Persian carpets, the transformation of Mughal carpet design from its Persian origins remains an underexplored area of research. Understanding this evolution is significant for several reasons. First, it provides insights into the artistic adaptation and innovation that occurred within the Mughal Empire, demonstrating how Persian influences were absorbed, modified, and reinterpreted to suit local tastes. The fusion of Persian symmetry with Mughal realism and botanical naturalism represents a unique cultural synthesis that speaks to the empire's broader artistic and architectural achievements. Second, the study highlights the role of trade, diplomacy, and royal patronage in facilitating cross-cultural exchanges between Persia and the Indian subcontinent. The Mughal emperors, particularly Akbar, Jahangir, and Shah Jahan, played a crucial role in fostering this artistic exchange, commissioning carpets that blended Persian techniques with distinct Mughal aesthetics.

Furthermore, analyzing the evolution of Mughal carpets in comparison to Persian carpets contributes to a broader understanding of how textiles functioned as cultural artifacts. Carpets were not only luxury commodities but also symbols of power, status, and artistic excellence. Their designs reflected the social, religious, and aesthetic values of their respective cultures, making them valuable historical documents. By examining motifs, color schemes, weaving methods, materials, and pattern compositions, this research aims to uncover the nuanced transformations that occurred as Mughal artisans adapted Persian influences to develop a unique visual language.

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This study is particularly relevant in the context of global textile heritage. Persian and Mughal carpets continue to inspire contemporary textile design, and understanding their evolution offers valuable lessons in cross-cultural artistic exchange. By addressing this gap in research, this study seeks to contribute to the appreciation of carpet weaving as an evolving art form that transcends geographical and temporal boundaries, shaping both historical and modern design sensibilities.

1.1 Research Questions

Building on the existing literature, this study formulates the following key research questions:

- i. What were the key similarities and differences between Persian and Mughal carpet designs in terms of motifs, color palettes, weaving techniques, and compositions?
- ii. How did trade, diplomacy, and cultural exchanges between Persia and the Mughal Empire influence carpet weaving traditions?
- iii. What is the lasting impact of Persian and Mughal carpets on global textile heritage and contemporary design sensibilities?

2. Review of Literature

The study of Persian and Mughal carpet aesthetics is fundamentally based on the broader theoretical constructs of creative adaptation, cultural hybridity, and textile historiography. Historically, textiles have functioned as essential cultural artifacts that mirror the social, political, and economic exchanges among civilizations [4]. Carpet weaving is acknowledged as both an artistic tradition and a dynamic craft influenced by regional factors and external interactions [5].

Prior studies on Persian carpets have predominantly concentrated on their symbolism, artistry, and significance within Safavid court culture [6, 7]. Researchers have emphasized the importance of geometric symmetry, arabesques, and floral patterns in Persian carpets, frequently linked to notions of divine perfection, paradise, and cosmic order [8]. These carpets had intricate designs that conformed to rigorous mathematical perfection, embodying the philosophical and aesthetic tenets of Persian creativity.

On the contrary, the Mughal Empire, which arose in India during the 16th century, was significantly shaped by Persian creative traditions, especially in the initial stages of its carpet manufacture [9]. Over time, Mughal artists integrated Persian techniques with native Indian aesthetics, resulting in a unique visual identity. This shift can be examined via the lens of cross-cultural artistic exchange [10], which investigates the absorption, modification, and reinterpretation of artistic traditions across many cultural contexts.

The Mughal methodology in carpet design was shaped by their admiration for naturalism, botanical accuracy, and vivid

colour schemes, deriving inspiration from India's abundant flora and animals [11]. In contrast to Persian carpets, which prioritized structured geometric designs, Mughal carpets frequently illustrated verdant gardens, flowering plants, avian species, and fauna, yielding a more organic and dynamic aesthetic. This transition exemplified a wider tendency in Mughal art and architecture, illustrated by miniature paintings and garden designs commissioned by emperors like Akbar, Jahangir, and Shah Jahan [12].

The historical development of Persian carpets has been thoroughly documented, with researchers analyzing their materials, techniques, trade networks, and symbolic significance [13]. The evolution of Mughal carpet design as a unique creative development separate from Persian traditions has been insufficiently investigated. Historians recognize that Mughal carpets were influenced by Persian designs, although the precise methods by which they deviated and evolved their distinctive stylistic features remain inadequately examined. Nonetheless, there has been no scholarly attention on how these contacts directly impacted the development of Mughal carpet weaving skills and artistic sensibilities. This study seeks to address this disparity through a comparative visual and textual examination of Persian and Mughal carpets, investigating the subtle shifts in design motifs, colour palettes, weaving techniques, and overall composition.

2.1 Evolution of Persian carpet weaving and its influence on the Mughal Empire

The history of Persian carpet weaving extends across centuries, characterized by developments in methods, themes, and cultural symbolism. Persian carpets, which originated over 2,500 years ago, attained prominence during the Safavid era, especially under Shah Abbas I, the emperor who founded royal workshops in Isfahan, Kashan, and Tabriz [14]. These workshops enhanced complex knotting techniques, vivid colours, and motifs, including medallions, arabesques, and garden themes representing paradise. Persian carpets gained significant demand throughout trade routes, impacting worldwide creative traditions, notably those of the Mughal Empire [15]. Akbar, the Emperor Mughals amalgamated Persian weaving techniques with Indian themes, allowing Persian weavers to set up workshops in Agra and Lahore. His successors, Jahangir and Shah Jahan, enhanced Mughal carpet-making by integrating Persian sophistication with indigenous artistic sensitivities [16]. This artistic amalgamation produced a unique Mughal style, embodying both Persian expertise and Indian cultural elements, thereby reinforcing the global legacy of Persian-influenced carpet making.

2.2 Influence of Trade Routes: Mughal Emperors' Adaptation of Persian Aesthetics

The exchange of culture through trade routes was essential in the Mughal Empire, enabling Mughal monarchs to include and modify Persian motifs in various creative forms, particularly carpets. The Mughal rulers, Akbar and his

successors, embraced Persian aesthetics, viewing them as emblems of luxury and sophistication [17]. Persian artisans and their exquisite works, including medallions, floral motifs, and opulent landscape designs, became esteemed in the Mughal court due to trade. Indian artisans created and adapted these designs, including native materials, motifs, and symbols, culminating in a unique style that reflected the cultural fusion of Persian sophistication and Indian artistic identity [18]. The incorporation of Persian artistry significantly impacted the local economy, leading to the establishment of vibrant workshops in cities like Agra and Lahore, where Persian artisans collaborated with Indian weavers. This relationship created jobs for local artisans and revitalized the textile industry, promoting economic growth through the production of exquisite carpets for both domestic and international markets. Mughal carpets, embedded with Persian motifs, became emblems of imperial grandeur, reflecting the emperors' authority and cultural significance while illustrating the dynamic interactions between Persian and Indian cultures, thereby creating a legacy of artistic synergy that enriched both traditions.

3. Methodology

This research employs a qualitative, comparative methodology to examine how the Mughal Empire reinterpreted Persian carpet aesthetics. The study examines the development of themes, colour schemes, weaving methods, and design compositions using historical writings, archival documents, and visual data. Selected Persian and Mughal carpets are subjected to a thorough visual examination to spot advances and stylistic parallels. Both primary and secondary sources were used to get the data for this study. Historical manuscripts are examples of primary sources. Scholarly texts, art historical journals, and historical trade records are examples of secondary sources. Through the use of an integrative methodology, it is possible to gain a deeper knowledge of how Mughal carpets incorporated Persian aesthetics, demonstrating both artistic innovation and cross-cultural discourse within the region's textile traditions.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Craftsmanship and Techniques

4.1.1 Persian weaving techniques and knot styles

Persian carpet weaving is intricately rooted in Iranian culture and heritage, with each region nurturing its weaving techniques, knotting patterns, motifs, and colour schemes. Persian carpets are distinguished by their superior craftsmanship, intricate designs, and the use of premium natural materials such as wool, silk, and cotton.

Persian carpets are known for two main types of knots:

4.1.1.1 Persian (Senneh) Knot–Asymmetrical Knot

This knot (Figure 1A) includes a single warp and crosses behind another warp before being pulled through. This

asymmetry enhances design precision and fine details, making it the optimal technique for producing high-quality carpets with rich floral and curvilinear themes. Carpets from Isfahan, Nain, Qom, and Kashan are often noted for their elaborate designs and luxurious silk or wool textures.

4.1.1.2 Turkish (Ghiordes) Knot–Symmetrical Knot

This technique entails (Figure 1B) encircling the yarn around two adjacent warp threads and drawing it through the Centre of the loop. This results in a denser and more durable weave, improving the carpet's density and strength [19]. It is employed in Tabriz and tribal carpets, especially those made by Bakhtiari and Kurdish craftsmen.

Figure 1: (A) Asymmetrical Knot, (B) Symmetrical Knot

4.2 Mughal adaptations: blending Persian techniques with Indian motifs and materials

The Mughal Empire symbolized a period of artistic synthesis marked by the harmonious amalgamation of Persian influences and Indian cultural aspects, particularly in carpet making. The weaving techniques of Mughal carpets were profoundly influenced by Persian artistry, while also incorporating Indian adaptations, culminating in a unique Indo-Persian textile legacy. Mughal carpets were founded on the asymmetrical Persian (Senneh) knot, enabling exquisite elaboration and sophisticated curvilinear patterns. This method, brought to India by Persian craftsmen, enabled the creation of exquisitely detailed floral, medallion, and arabesque patterns. The warp and weft structures were initially influenced by Persian designs; however, Indian weavers integrated cotton warps for increased durability with silk or pashmina wool for a more refined texture. The knot density in Mughal carpets was exceptionally high, often exceeding 1,000 knots per square inch, making them some of the finest carpets for their time.

Persian carpets notably follow highly structured designs, often with a central medallion, symmetrical borders, and repetitive floral motifs. Under Mughal influence, these patterns evolved to embrace a more organic and dynamic look. Mughal carpets displayed spontaneous, fluid floral designs that more accurately reflected nature, rather than succumbing to rigid repetition [20]. The Mughals used narrative and figurative elements, such as hunting scenes, depictions of animals, and courtly figures motifs, rare in Persian carpets yet characteristic of Mughal craftsmanship [21].

4.2 Expanding the Persian Color Palette with Indian Innovations in the Mughal Period

The colour innovations in Mughal carpets were significantly influenced by Persian dyeing traditions, though they were greatly enhanced by the incorporation of Indian natural dyes. Persian carpets traditionally exhibited a rich but limited colour palette, primarily consisting of deep reds, blues, and ivory hues, sourced from natural materials such as cochineal, madder root, indigo, and pomegranate rinds. The colours were carefully layered to establish contrast and depth, with Persian weavers typically preferring evident symmetrical designs that accentuated elaborate floral and geometric patterns. The introduction of Persian weaving techniques to India under Mughal patronage resulted in a transformation of the colour palette, incorporating a wide range of Indian botanical and mineral dyes. The Mughals added more vivid and varied hues to their carpets while retaining the Persian skill at creating durable, fade-resistant colours [22]. The introduction of indigo from Rajasthan intensified the blues, while lac and madder root from Gujarat enhanced the reds with a more nuanced spectrum, spanning from crimson to burgundy. Turmeric from Bengal provided vibrant golden yellows, enhancing floral and architectural designs, while pomegranate rinds and saffron from Kashmir offered deep brown and golden tones, facilitating detailed shading and depth. The advancement in dyeing techniques not only improved the aesthetic allure of Mughal carpets but also positioned them as some of the most opulent and coveted textiles in both Indian and global markets.

Figure 2: Persian and Expanded Mughal Carpet Color Palette

4.3 Design and Motif Analysis

4.3.1 Common Themes and Symbolism

Persian and Mughal carpets are renowned for their intricate designs and deep symbolism, reflecting the cultural, religious, and philosophical ideals of their respective periods. Both traditions often highlight themes like nature, spirituality, and the depiction of ideal gardens, incorporating elements such as flowers, vines, trees, and animals. These elements symbolize life, eternity, and divine beauty, influenced by Islamic and regional motifs [23]. Geometric patterns, arabesques, and medallions are prevalent in both genres, symbolizing oneness, harmony, and the limitless nature of the world. Mythological and spiritual symbols, such as the Tree of Life, frequently represent the connection

between the terrestrial and the celestial. Persian carpets exemplify elegance and precision with symmetrical designs, while Mughal carpets integrate Indo-Persian aesthetics with a more naturalistic depiction of flora and wildlife. These carpets collectively reflect the shared legacy and intercultural connections between the Persian and Mughal empires, creating a tale of beauty and symbolism that transcends historical bounds.

Figure 3: Tree of Life Designs according to different cultures

All religions that believe in one God share the tree as a common theme. Cypress, date palm, pomegranate, fig, olive, wine, beech, and oak are just a few of the plants that have been used as symbols of the tree of life by different cultures. The Tree of Life (Figure 3) is both a symbol of death and a link between the three realms (this world, the next, and the afterlife) in Turkish mythology, where it is believed to have originated. Even though the boy's body will eventually die, his soul will remain eternally, and the tree of life will reveal its future path. Mughal carpets featuring the Tree of Life represented paradise (Jannat), prosperity, and eternity. Its beautiful woven designs, which blended Persian and Indian influences, reflected imperial grandeur and spiritual symbolism; they featured floral patterns, birds, and vines [24].

4.3.2 The distinct iconography of motifs in Persian and Mughal carpets

The iconography of Persian and Mughal carpet motifs reflects their rich artistic traditions and cultural heritage, combining aesthetic beauty with symbolic depth. Carpets served both practical and symbolic functions, representing a magical space where the border signified the terrestrial realm and the field symbolized the divine. Persian and Mughal carpets feature three primary ornamental groups. The first includes geometric motifs like eight-pointed stars (Figure 4), swastikas, and hooked diamonds, filling open spaces. The second consists of floral and leaf patterns, notably the rosette and palmette, the latter being especially prominent in Persian design since the 16th century.

The third group comprises distinctive motifs unique to specific regions, appearing in both field and border designs. This iconographic richness showcases artisans' skill while preserving cultural narratives, beliefs, and values through intricate patterns, making carpets enduring artistic and historical records.

Figure 4: "s" shaped Designs and eight-pointed star Patterns

4.3.2.1 Floral Motifs

Floral motifs are integral to both Persian and Mughal carpets, symbolizing paradise, beauty, and the harmony of the natural world. Persian carpets frequently feature floral motifs, including stylized depictions of the lotus, lilies, roses, and the cypress tree, which represent eternity and resolve. Typically arranged in the *chahar bagh* (four-garden) layout, these designs embody the Persian ideal of paradise as a lush, orderly garden, symbolizing beauty, abundance, and a harmonious connection with nature.

The lotus, a repeating motif, symbolizes purity and spiritual enlightenment, illustrating its profound association with Persian intellectual and mystical traditions.

i) Rose: Frequently illustrated in stylized clusters, the rose represents divine love and the ephemeral essence of worldly beauty.

ii) Cypress Tree: A towering, evergreen tree frequently depicted in Persian art, the cypress represents longevity and resilience, serving as a metaphor for strength in the face of hardship.

iii) Shah Abbasi Design: This design (Figure 5A) is characterized by symmetrical arrays of stylized floral patterns, predominantly lotus and palmettes, emanating from a central medallion. It represents unity, order, and the prominence of the divine presence.

Figure 5: A) Shah Abbasi Motif, B) Lotus Flower, and C) Tulips

Mughal carpets exhibit considerable Persian influence while using native Indian flora, including the lotus, Champa, and marigold, thus enhancing the designs with local symbolism and aesthetic appeal. Mughal artists favoured realistic depictions, illustrating flowers with meticulous botanical precision that reflected the emperors' fascination with the natural world. These carpets also exhibit floral arrangements,

like flowering plants in vases or blossoming trees, mirroring the Mughal kings' affinity for gardens and their idealized representation of paradise [25]. Under Akbar's reign, the garden symbolized paradise, and flower motifs on Mughal carpets often encapsulated this idea, blending Persian stylization with Indian authenticity.

i) Lotus: It (Figure 5B) maintains its symbolic connection to purity and enlightenment, although it is depicted in gentler, more naturalistic forms. This reflects its hallowed importance in Indian culture and its Islamic implications.
ii) Chrysanthemum, Iris, and Tulip: These flowers (Figure 5C), frequently illustrated in full bloom, exemplify Mughal artistic sophistication and their admiration for natural beauty.
iii) Charbagh Layouts: In contrast to Persian carpets that utilize stylized garden motifs (Figure 6), Mughal carpets sometimes integrate garden layouts directly into their designs. Separated by paths or flowing water channels, these carpets reflect the architectural elegance of Mughal gardens such as Shalimar Bagh.

Figure 6: The Chahar Bagh Rug at The Albert Hall Museum In Jaipur (Image Source: <https://nazmiyalantiquerugs.com/blog/indo-persian-chahar-bagh-gardens-and-rugs>)

4.3.2.2 Arabesque Patterns

Arabesque patterns (Figure 7A), consisting of flowing, symmetrical curves and interlacing lines, are essential to Persian and Mughal designs, representing infinity and divine harmony. In Persian carpets, arabesques are exceptionally comprehensive, with rhythmic details that symbolize the timeless essence of the world and divine creation. Persian arabesques, which are frequently paired with floral patterns and center medallions, represent a mystical perspective that echoes Sufi ideas of interconnectivity. These patterns integrate effortlessly with other design aspects, establishing an overall flow that encapsulates both intricacy and spiritual balance [26].

Arabesques have a softer approach in Mughal carpets (Figure 7B), merging well with vegetal and floral patterns to create a more natural and realistic look. Mughal artists preferred scrolling vines and intertwined floral motifs, imparting a feeling of development, connectedness, and equilibrium that embodies Indian aesthetic concepts [27]. Therefore, although influenced by Persian designs, Mughal arabesques offer a more fluid and organic rendition, reflecting the empire's admiration for creative amalgamation and the elegance of nature.

Figure 7: (A) *Safavid Arabesque carpet fragment, 16th century, Iran. Austrian Museum of Art, (B) Indo-Persian carpet with floral carpet with palmettes, Herati and arabesque pattern*

4.3.2.3 Animal Patterns

Animal motifs in Persian and Mughal carpets reveal distinct approaches, though both traditions use animals to convey power, grace, and divine symbolism. Animal images on Persian carpets (Figure 8A) are frequently stylized and tastefully incorporated into garden or hunting motifs. Mythological animals with strong symbolic significance, such as dragons, griffins, and Simurghs (Persian phoenix), represent cosmic order, knowledge, and protection. The Simurgh represents knowledge and longevity, whilst dragons signify guardianship and might. Animal themes in Persian artwork are frequently abstracted to emphasize symbolic rather than literal depiction because it is strictly prohibited by Islam to show live things [28].

Mughal carpets (Figure 8B), however, portray animals more boldly and with naturalistic detail, reflecting the Mughal fascination with the natural world and hunting culture. Indigenous fauna such as elephants, peacocks, tigers, and deer are shown with meticulous accuracy, reflecting the Mughals' admiration for realism and their affinity for the Indian ecosystem. Peacocks signify beauty and immortality, and elephants denote strength and regal majesty, enhancing the carpets' symbolism of royal power. Animal themes in Mughal carpets often depict hunting or garden settings, blending Persian-inspired designs with uniquely Indian portrayals of nature and elegant existence [29].

8A

8B

Figure 8: (A) *Safavid carpet, Herat, mid-16th–early 17th century, Shah Tahmasb I or Muhammed Khudabanda Period, (B) The Thyssen Mughal Hunting Carpet at Sotheby's – HALI*

4.3.2.4 Geometric Patterns

Geometric patterns (Figure 9A, 9B, 9C) play a vital role in both Persian and Mughal carpet traditions, representing cosmic order, unity, and harmony. Persian carpets typically exhibit intricate geometric grids, star motifs, and medallions, symbolizing balance and spiritual unity. Persian artists used geometry to develop a systematic arrangement that reflected the belief in the harmony of the world [30]. These designs represent a belief in a divine, harmonious universe, where intricately structured patterns signify an appreciation for balance and spiritual values. Medallions, frequently employed as focal points, represent oneness with geometric shapes that extend outward in complex, mathematically exact patterns reflecting Persian religion and mythology.

In Mughal carpets, geometric designs retain significant value, however, they are softened by the use of floral and naturalistic elements. Mughal artists preserved the symmetry of geometric shapes while integrating floral motifs, vines, and arabesque designs (Figure 9D), achieving a harmonious balance between fixed order and natural beauty [31]. Mughal carpets frequently have medallion-centered designs encircled by flowing floral motifs, blending geometric accuracy with a natural harmony that reflects Indian creative values. The outcome is a unique Mughal interpretation of geometry that respects the structured, spiritual importance of the Persian style while embracing the softer, naturalistic beauty of Indian art [32].

Figure 9: (A) *geometric botah, (B) Star Medallion, (C) Peacock motif on the Persian Carpet, (D) 17th Century Mughal Carpet*

(Image source: A, B & C <https://letsGOPersian.com/blog/decoding-traditional-motifs-and-designs-in-persian-carpets/>, D <https://www.theculturegully.in/post/the-mughal-legacy-in-india-s-carpet-industry-from-agra-to-the-world>)

4.4 Differences in the Iconography of Persian and Mughal Carpet

Persian carpets are renowned for their stylized floral, arabesque, and geometric motifs, often featuring medallion designs that incorporate symbolic representations of paradise and divine order. In contrast, Mughal carpets, though inspired by Persian tradition, display naturalistic

flowers, birds, and animals with a strong sense of realism influenced by miniature paintings. Thus, while Persian iconography emphasizes abstraction and symbolism, Mughal carpets highlight naturalism and a fusion of Persian and Indian artistic elements. Here is the iconography of Persian and Mughal carpets

Table 1: Iconography of Persian and Mughal Carpet

Aspects	Persian Carpet	Mughal Carpet
Historical Context	Developed over thousands of years, with significant advancements during the Safavid Dynasty(1501-1736). Persian carpets were highly prized both domestically and internationally, and often used as diplomatic gifts. The art form reflects the socio-political context of Persia, showcasing the empire's wealth and craftsmanship.	Flourished during the Mughal Empire from 1526 to 1858. Significant patronage from emperors like Akbar, Jahangir, and Shah Jahan, who established royal workshops. The period is marked by a blending of Persian art with Indian influences due to extensive cultural exchange.
Influences	Influenced by various cultures including Mongol, Tatar, and Islamic artistic traditions. Persian carpets often served as models for other Islamic carpet-making traditions across the region. The Safavid period saw an influx of artistic ideas from China and Europe, further enriching Persian designs.	Heavily influenced by Persian designs, Mughal artisans adapted these styles to incorporate local themes and motifs. The interaction with European art through trade introduced new elements to Mughal designs. Indian flora and fauna were integrated into traditional Persian patterns, creating a unique hybrid style.
Common Motifs	Rich floral motifs, including palmettes, arabesques, and stylized flowers, dominate the designs. Geometric patterns are highly developed, often forming complex repeat designs that convey symmetry and harmony. Calligraphy may be incorporated into borders or central medallions as a reflection of Islamic art.	Predominantly floral patterns featuring roses, lotuses, and intricate vine scrolls. Geometric shapes are used but often blended with organic forms; motifs like medallions are common. Scenic landscapes often depict gardens or nature scenes, symbolizing paradise.
Notable Techniques	Notable for the 'Vase Technique' where vases filled with flowers are depicted prominently; intricate knotting methods allow for detailed imagery that is both delicate and durable. - Use of rich colors achieved through natural dyes like indigo and cochineal creates striking visual contrasts within patterns.	- High knot density (up to 500 knots per square inch) allows for detailed imagery; complex weaving techniques recorded in Ta'lim(manuals). - Use of vibrant dyes derived from natural sources enhances color richness; techniques like abrash (color variations) add depth to designs.
Color Symbolism	Symbolic and Traditional: Red (power and passion), blue (spirituality), green (paradise, used minimally due to religious context), black (mystery). Deep, vibrant hues dominate.	Rich, Luxurious, and Natural Tones: Red, green, gold, blue, and yellow, reflecting royalty and wealth. Green symbolizes paradise, while gold represents luxury and divine grace. Colors tend to be softer and more naturalistic than Persian carpets.
Floral Motifs	Stylized and Geometric: Common flowers include lotus, cypress, and palmette, arranged symmetrically. Symbolize purity and eternity.	Naturalistic and Detailed: Flowers like lotus, tulip, iris, and poppy, are depicted with lifelike detail. Reflect the lush Indian flora. Represent paradise on earth.
Botanical Layouts	Symmetrical, Structured Gardens: Designs often follow a structured layout with repeating floral patterns, aiming to represent cosmic order and harmony.	Garden-inspired with Quadrants (Chahar Bagh): Inspired by Mughal gardens, motifs are often placed in garden-like layouts, representing paradise gardens with detailed flower beds.

Aspects	Persian Carpet	Mughal Carpet
Animal Symbols	Mythical and Symbolic Animals: Lions, gazelles, and mythical creatures like dragons and phoenixes symbolize strength, spirituality, and protection. Deer and Gazelles : Symbolizing grace and beauty.	Naturalistic Animals, Inspired by Hunting: Tigers, elephants, peacocks, parrots, and cranes, representing royalty, grace, and Mughal power. Hunting scenes symbolize power and dominion
Bird Iconography	Nightingale and Peacock: Nightingales symbolize divine love, while peacocks represent immortality and beauty. Often rendered symbolically	Peacock, Parrot, Crane: These birds are rendered in a lifelike manner, symbolizing beauty, wisdom, and grace. Reflect the Mughal admiration for the natural world.
Geometric and Abstract Patterns	Highly Stylized Patterns: Emphasis on abstract geometry, symmetry, and balance, creating a sense of divine harmony. Borders and medallions reinforce cosmic structure.	Less Geometric, More Realistic Forms: Geometric elements are present but secondary to floral and animal patterns. Emphasis is on naturalistic designs, reflecting realism and the Mughal love of nature.
Central Medallion	Unified Focal Point: Large central medallions represent cosmic harmony, with floral and geometric symmetry that embodies the universe's order.	Paradise Garden Layout: Central medallions exist but often take the form of garden-inspired layouts. Carpet interiors may be divided into quadrants filled with florals and animal motifs.
Architectural Influence	Cosmic Medallions and Borders: Medallions represent the center of the universe or paradise garden. Borders are heavily patterned, signifying protection and framing.	Mughal Palace and Garden Elements: Arches, mihrabs, and symmetrical quadrants resemble Mughal architectural styles. Designs often mimic Mughal palaces and chahar bagh gardens.
Religious and Mystical Themes	Islamic and Sufi Influence: The Tree of Life symbolizes the path from earthly life to the divine. The carpet itself represents the cosmos or paradise garden, bridging earth and heaven.	Islamic Paradise with Earthly Elements: Mihrabs on prayer rugs symbolize direction in prayer. Garden layouts emphasize the earthly paradise, celebrating nature's beauty and Mughal opulence.
Influence of Sufi Mysticism	High: Sufi themes like unity with the divine are prevalent; nightingales, flowers, and trees often represent spiritual concepts such as divine love and the soul's journey.	Moderate: Sufi influence is subtle, seen in harmonious and balanced designs. More focus on earthly beauty and the symbolism of paradise rather than the spiritual journey.
Cultural Fusion	Persian, Zoroastrian, and Islamic Elements: Deeply influenced by ancient Persian mythology, Zoroastrianism, and Islamic spirituality, creating a unique fusion of styles.	Indian, Persian, and Islamic Blending: Combines Persian influences with Indian aesthetics, integrating local fauna, flora, and architectural elements, creating a distinct Mughal style.
Cultural Fusion	Persian, Zoroastrian, and Islamic Elements: Deeply influenced by ancient Persian mythology, Zoroastrianism, and Islamic spirituality, creating a unique fusion of styles.	Indian, Persian, and Islamic Blending: Combines Persian influences with Indian aesthetics, integrating local fauna, flora, and architectural elements, creating a distinct Mughal style.
Overall Aesthetic	Stylized, Formal, and Symbolic: Emphasis on symmetry, cosmic symbolism, and spiritual depth. Designs often appear structured and idealized.	Naturalistic, Opulent, and Realistic: More lifelike depictions, reflecting the grandeur of Mughal courts and admiration for nature. Designs focus on lush, realistic beauty with rich colors and opulent details.

Persian carpets, which draw inspiration from Islamic art and ancient Persian spirituality, feature geometrical patterns that emphasize cosmic harmony and mysticism. By fusing Persian, Indian, and Islamic themes into a distinctive style, Mughal carpets emphasize opulence and naturalism, reflecting the Mughals' adoration for India's abundant flora and fauna, architectural magnificence, and the idea of an earthly paradise.

5. Conclusion

The artistic evolution of Persian and Mughal carpet designs reflects a rich narrative of cultural exchange, adaptation, and innovation. Persian carpets, renowned for their curvilinear

precision, masterful weaving, and symbolic motifs, emphasize structural harmony, symmetry, and elaborate arabesques. Typically centered on medallions or lattice frameworks, they feature scrolling vines, stylized floral motifs, and deep, saturated jewel tones like blues, reds, and golds, enhancing their grandeur. Mughal carpets, initially influenced by Persian aesthetics, evolved as Indian artisans infused indigenous elements, regional craftsmanship, and distinctive color palettes. While sharing common motifs like arabesques and floral patterns, Mughal designs exhibit a shift toward naturalistic floral arrangements, delicate shading, and an open composition. Inspired by Indian miniature paintings

and botanical studies, they depict realistic flowers, birds, and fauna, favoring subtle pastels and natural hues over bold Persian contrasts.

This comparative analysis highlights how Persian carpets prioritize order, symmetry, and opulence, whereas Mughal carpets embrace fluidity, realism, and elegance. Despite Persian influence, Mughal carpets developed a unique

identity, reflecting a fusion of foreign and local traditions. Their artistic and cultural significance extends beyond aesthetics, serving as historical artifacts that embody the dynamic exchange of design traditions. Understanding these nuances enriches our appreciation of textile heritage and underscores carpets as enduring symbols of artistic mastery and cross-cultural influence.

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